

PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS' WELFARE AND QUALITY OF TEACHING UPON IMPLEMENTATION OF THE IMMEDIATE REMOVAL OF ADMINISTRATIVE TASKS IN CANDELARIA, ZAMBALES

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KeyWords

Teacher welfare, quality of teaching, DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024, administrative tasks, non-teaching tasks, ancillary services

ABSTRACT

The study addresses the impact of the removal of administrative responsibilities on public high school teachers' welfare and teaching quality in the district of Candelaria, Zambales, following the implementation of DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024. Using quantitative, cross-sectional design and structured questionnaires, this research assessed teachers' welfare and teaching quality. Findings indicate that teachers generally agree on the state of their welfare, expressing higher satisfaction in community respect and professional development but lower satisfaction in salary, health, and retirement benefits. Teachers rated their teaching quality highly, with the greatest satisfaction in the learning environment and personal growth, although content knowledge and pedagogy received slightly lower ratings. The results also show that the number of subject preparations significantly impacts teachers' welfare, while the number of teaching loads significantly affects teaching quality. Additionally, a positive correlation was found between teachers' welfare and their quality of teaching, suggesting that enhanced welfare may contribute to higher teaching quality.

INTRODUCTION

On January 26, 2024, Philippine Vice President and then-Education Secretary Sara Duterte signed Department of Education (DepEd) Order No. 2, s. 2024, establishing a policy to immediately relieve public school teachers of administrative or non-teaching duties. Part of the *MATATAG* agenda, this order aims to enhance *teachers' welfare* and improve *the quality of education* by allowing teachers more time to focus on classroom instruction (Chi, 2023; Marcelo, 2024; Relativo, 2024).

The well-being of teachers is essential to the quality of education, as teachers are key contributors to the learning and academic achievement of the students. However, in the Philippines, public school teachers frequently shoulder non-teaching duties, including clerical work, administrative tasks, and extracurricular supervision. These additional responsibilities limit the time and energy they can dedicate to their primary role in delivering quality teaching (Abasola, 2024). These have raised concerns about the effects of such burdens on teacher welfare and teaching quality. To address these issues, this study investigated the welfare and quality of teaching of public high school teachers in Candelaria, Zambales upon implementation of the immediate removal of administrative tasks as mandated by DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024.

Existing studies indicate that the workload of Filipino teachers, particularly the inclusion of administrative duties, contributes to high levels of job stress, burnout, and a decline in the overall quality of teaching. A report by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) highlighted that Filipino teachers spend a significant portion of their working hours on non-teaching tasks, which limits their ability to focus on lesson planning and student engagement (Cigalal, 2019). Furthermore, in a long paper analysis by Tarraya (2023) revealed that administrative workload was one of the leading causes of inefficiency in teaching. Although there have been

efforts to reduce administrative tasks, these interventions have not been thoroughly examined in relation to their effect on teaching quality and teacher welfare.

This study is essential as it aims to assess the impact of removing non-teaching responsibilities on the welfare of public high school teachers and, consequently, on their teaching effectiveness. The findings could guide the Department of Education in implementing targeted reforms to reduce teachers' administrative workload. Since teacher welfare is strongly connected to student success, improving teachers' working conditions could have significant benefits for educational quality in the country.

OBJECTIVE

This study aims to evaluate the welfare and quality of teaching among public high school teachers in the district of Candelaria, Zambales, following the implementation of DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024, which mandates the removal of administrative tasks.

Specifically, the study seeks to understand the profile of teacher-respondents by examining their gender, age, civil status, teaching position, years of service, number of preparations or subjects taught, teaching load, and assigned ancillary services. It also aims to identify the types of non-teaching tasks that were previously assigned to teachers.

Furthermore, the study explores how teachers perceive their welfare after the removal of administrative tasks, focusing on aspects such as (a) salary and compensation, (b) workload and work-life balance, (c) professional development, (d) health and well-being, (e) government and institutional support, (f) community respect and recognition, (g) technology and infrastructure, (h) safety and security, and (i) retirement benefits. Additionally, it examines how teachers assess their quality of teaching based on the seven domains of the *Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)*, including (a) content knowledge and pedagogy, (b) learning environment, (c) diversity of learners, (d) curriculum and planning, (e) assessment and reporting, (f) community linkages and professional engagement, and (g) personal and professional growth.

The study also investigates whether significant differences exist in teacher welfare and quality of teaching when grouped according to their demographic and professional profile. Lastly, it seeks to determine whether a significant relationship exists between teachers' welfare and their quality of teaching after the removal of administrative tasks.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey research design aimed at exploring the welfare and quality of teaching among public high school teachers in Candelaria, Zambales. Using a structured questionnaire, this design allows the collection of data at a single point in time from a representative sample of teachers, enabling a systematic assessment of their welfare and teaching quality as well as any relationships with demographic characteristics.

To achieve the study's objectives, descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the profiles of the teacher-respondents. Inferential statistics such as Mann-Whiney U Test and Kruskal-Wallis Test were conducted to examine whether significant differences exist in teachers' welfare and quality of teaching when grouped by these profile variables. Additionally, correlation analysis, such as Spearman's rho, was applied to explore any potential relationship between teachers' welfare and teaching quality.

A priori sample size estimation was conducted using *GPower 3.1.9.7* (Faul et al., 2007) to determine the required sample size for a correlation analysis. The calculation was based on a medium effect size ($*r = 0.30$), an alpha level of 0.05, and a desired power of 0.85. The results indicated that a minimum of 77 respondents was needed to achieve sufficient power for detecting a significant correlation. Utilizing stratified random sampling, the 77 public high school teacher-respondents were distributed among the four public schools within the district of Candelaria, Zambales.

School	Male	Female	N	Male	Female	n
Public School 1	9	28	37	6	17	23
Public School 2	12	23	35	7	14	21
Public School 3	10	29	39	6	18	24
Public School 4	4	11	15	2	7	9
Total	35	91	126	21	56	77

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

In terms of gender, the majority of the participants are female, accounting for 72.73% (56 individuals), while male teachers make up 27.27% (21 individuals). Regarding age, the largest group of respondents falls within the early middle-age category (40-44 years old), representing 25.97% (20 individuals). This is followed closely by the young adult group (30-34 years old), comprising 23.38% (18 individuals). The least represented age groups include those aged 50-54 years (3.90%) and 60-64 years (2.60%). The computed mean age of 39.40 years suggests that most teachers in the sample belong to the young to early middle-age range (Dyussenbayev, 2017).

With regard to civil status, the majority of respondents are married (63.64%, 49 individuals), while single teachers constitute

31.17% (24 individuals). A smaller percentage, 5.19% (4 individuals), are widowed. In terms of teaching position, the most common rank among respondents is Teacher I, with 45.45% (35 individuals) holding this position. This is followed by Teacher III (29.87%, 23 individuals) and Teacher II (24.68%, 19 individuals), indicating a distribution across different teaching levels.

When considering years in service, the largest proportion of teachers have 5-9 years of experience (25.97%), closely followed by those with 0-4 years (24.68%). A smaller percentage has been in the profession for 10-14 years (20.78%) and 15-19 years (14.28%). The computed mean of 11.94 years suggests that most teachers are in their early to mid-career stages.

Regarding the number of preparations or subjects taught, the majority handle 2 subjects (44.16%), followed by those teaching 3 subjects (32.47%). This indicates that most teachers manage multiple subject preparations, with an overall mean of 3.26 subjects. In terms of teaching load, most respondents handle 6 classes (36.36%), followed by those managing 4 classes (22.07%) and 5 classes (20.78%). The computed mean teaching load of 4.82 classes highlights that teachers typically manage between 4 and 6 classes.

Finally, regarding ancillary services assigned, the majority of teachers are responsible for 3 non-teaching tasks (51.95%), while 28.57% handle 2 tasks. This suggests that most teachers juggle multiple non-teaching responsibilities, with an overall mean of 2.56 ancillary tasks.

Ancillary Services Assigned to Teachers

In this study, the teachers often take on additional responsibilities beyond their regular teaching duties, with the most common ancillary tasks being (1) class advisory, (2) subject area coordinatorship, and (3) grade level coordinatorship.

Area	Load Intensity	Ancillary Services	Frequency
Curriculum	Heavy	Class adviser	47
	Medium	Subject area coordinator	32
	Light	Phil-IRI coordinator	6
School Management	Heavy	Guidance coordinator	4
		ICT/LIS/EBEIS coordinator	3
		Health officer	2
		Sports coordinator	2
	Medium	Grade level coordinator	15
	Light	DRRM coordinator	2
		SBM coordinator	1
		Remedial class coordinator	2
SSG adviser		3	
Project/Program	Heavy	Gulayan coordinator	1
	Medium	School paper adviser	6
	Light	Child protection officer	4
		WINS coordinator	2
Inter-agency	Medium	Scouting coordinator	3
	Light	4Ps coordinator	3

Class advisory is the most demanding role, assigned to 47 teachers, requiring them to manage a class, handle administrative tasks, and support students' well-being. Subject area coordinatorship, assigned to 32 teachers, involves overseeing curriculum and activities within a subject, ensuring consistency in instruction. Grade level coordinatorship, handled by 15 teachers, focuses on student welfare and staff coordination within a grade level.

Public High School Teachers' Welfare

The table presents insights into the welfare of public school teachers across nine factors, with an overall grand mean of 2.95, indicating general agreement among teachers regarding their experiences and perceptions.

Teachers' Welfare Factor	Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
Salary and Compensation	2.83	Agree	8
Workload and Work-Life Balance	2.97	Agree	5
Professional Development	3.02	Agree	3
Health and Well-Being	2.84	Agree	7
Government & Institutional Support	2.90	Agree	6
Community Respect and Recognition	3.27	Strongly Agree	1
Technology and Infrastructure	3.03	Agree	2
Safety and Security	3.01	Agree	4

Retirement and Pension	2.72	Agree	9
Grand Mean	2.95	Agree	

Teachers strongly agree that they feel respected and recognized by their community, which contributes significantly to their overall job satisfaction (Rank 1, 3.27). Samano et al. (2024) examined students' perceptions of respecting teachers focusing on how grade level, age, and sex influence views on classroom conduct and manners. The study found no significant differences in perceptions of manners based on grade level or age, indicating consistent expectations of respectful behavior across these demographics. However, there were significant differences based on sex, with male and female students holding differing views on respectful behavior and classroom conduct. Perceptions of conduct varied significantly across grade levels, influenced by academic maturity and educational experiences, but age was not a determining factor. The findings highlight the importance of considering gender and grade-level dynamics in promoting respectful behavior. Educators are encouraged to develop interventions to address these differences, encouraging a more inclusive and respectful learning environment.

They also agree that the technology and infrastructure available are sufficient for their teaching needs, suggesting that resources are generally adequate to support effective instruction (Rank 2, 3.03). Teachers feel positive about the opportunities for professional development, reflecting an acknowledgment of the importance of ongoing training and skills enhancement for career growth (Rank 3, 3.02). They also feel secure in their work environment, which is essential for promoting a productive teaching and learning atmosphere (Rank 4, 3.01). In the study of Garcia and Cuevas (2019), results showed a significant positive relationship between workplace safety perceptions and work engagement. Specifically, the safety measures of co-teachers and school commitment to safety were found to significantly predict work engagement, with the school's commitment being the strongest predictor. The study highlighted that teachers' perception of workplace safety, involving co-teachers' actions and administrative commitment, promotes better engagement. Supportive leadership, a culture of safety, and effective safety programs enhance teachers' performance and satisfaction. It aligns with previous studies emphasizing the importance of leadership in prioritizing safety and creating a secure environment to boost organizational commitment and employee well-being. Ultimately, workplace safety is essential for cultivating a positive and engaged teaching workforce.

There is general agreement that teachers find their workload manageable, an essential factor for maintaining a healthy work-life balance (Rank 5, 2.97). Additionally, teachers view the support from governmental and institutional entities as generally positive (Rank 6, 2.90). While teachers agree on the support for health and well-being, some areas still need improvement to better address their physical and mental health (Rank 7, 2.84).

Teachers agree that their salary and compensation are adequate, though there is some dissatisfaction or a perceived need for improvement (Rank 8, 2.83). Lastly, while teachers generally agree on the adequacy of their retirement and pension benefits, notable concerns regarding long-term financial security could impact their overall sense of well-being (Rank 9, 2.72). Bangao (2020) revealed that retirement can be distressing due to issues like financial scams, illegal recruitment, loan burdens, lack of pension, and health risks such as mild strokes. Conversely, early retirement and preparedness were associated with a more comfortable post-retirement life. Retired teachers faced challenges, including limited social support and declining health, but many remained active in their communities. They contributed to initiatives such as anti-drug campaigns, women and child welfare, environmental protection, curfew enforcement, and peacekeeping. Some also volunteered in schools, teaching religious and values education.

Public High School Teachers' Quality of Teaching

The table provides insights into the quality of teaching among public school teachers across seven domains, with an overall grand mean of 3.50, indicating a high level of agreement and confidence in their teaching practices.

Quality of Teaching Domain	Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.47	Strongly Agree	7
Learning Environment	3.55	Strongly Agree	1
Diversity of Learners	3.49	Strongly Agree	4.5
Curriculum and Planning	3.49	Strongly Agree	4.5
Assessment and Reporting	3.49	Strongly Agree	4.5
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.50	Strongly Agree	3
Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.51	Strongly Agree	2
Grand Mean	3.50	Strongly Agree	

Teachers demonstrate a strong commitment to creating safe, supportive, and engaging classrooms that promote effective learning. This emphasizes teachers' dedication to maintaining spaces conducive to student growth (Ranked 1, 3.55). Almonia and Oliva (2022) investigated the moderating role of the classroom learning environment in the relationship between teacher creativity and student academic resilience. The results revealed that the classroom environment serves as a partial mediator in the relationship between teacher creativity and student academic resilience. This highlights the importance of promoting positive classroom envi-

ronments to enhance teacher creativity and student resilience.

Teachers also give emphasis on continuous improvement through goal setting, reflection, and participation in professional networks. This highlights an understanding of the importance of evolving in their profession to meet the changing needs of students (Ranked 2, 3.51). The teachers also value collaboration with the community and adhere to professional ethics, promoting trust and inclusivity within the educational environment (Ranked 3, 3.50). Teachers are strongly committed to adapting instruction to meet diverse needs, designing relevant learning programs, and utilizing effective assessment strategies to monitor and support student progress (Ranked 4, 3.49).

Finally, teachers are confident in their subject knowledge and instructional strategies, though this is an area where some feel additional resources or support may enhance their effectiveness (Rank 7, Mean 3.47). Manigbas et al. (2024) found in their study that teachers were highly competent overall but needed improvement in utilizing research-based knowledge and principles of teaching. Professional peers were identified as the most influential factor affecting their competencies. Quantitative data revealed that teachers' application of content knowledge across curriculum areas and their use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English were significantly influenced by their demographic characteristics. The study recommends that DepEd officials focus on providing targeted professional development programs to enhance teachers' competencies and improve classroom instruction. In a qualitative study by Dalagan and Dagansan (2023), findings revealed that teachers effectively applied content knowledge across curriculum areas by aligning lessons with learning competencies, using interactive activities, visual aids, songs, and stories, and enhancing literacy and numeracy skills through methods like worksheets and the Marungko approach. They also developed students' higher-order thinking skills by incorporating real-world problems and innovative teaching strategies. The study recommends further research focusing on other indicators of content knowledge and pedagogy to build a more comprehensive understanding of teachers' performance.

Difference between Public High School Teachers' Welfare when Grouped According to Profile Variables

The table summarizes the results of testing the differences between public high school teachers' welfare when grouped according to profile variables. Among the variables analyzed, only the number of preparations significantly impacts teachers' welfare. This finding emphasizes the challenges associated with handling multiple subjects, which could affect teachers' stress levels, work-life balance, and overall satisfaction.

Variable	Test	p	Interpretation
Gender	$U = 575.5$.886	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Age	$H = 2.758$.906	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Civil Status	$H = 3.456$.178	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Position	$H = .911$.634	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Number of Years in Service	$H = 9.925$.270	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Number of Preparations/Subjects Taught	$H = 12.958$.011	Reject H_0 ; Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	$H = 6.081$.530	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Number of Ancillary Services Assigned	$H = 1.321$.858	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant

Note: p-value $\leq .05$ – Significant; p-value $> .05$ – Not Significant

The table below shows that there is significant difference between public school teachers' welfare when grouped according to number of preparations, $H(4, N = 77) = 12.958, p = .011$, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that the number of preparations (or subjects taught) has a significant impact on teachers' welfare. Teachers handling different subjects experience varying levels of welfare, due to differences in workload and the associated demands of preparing for multiple subjects.

Number of Preparations	N	Mean Rank	df	χ^2	p	Interpretation
1	6	24.83	4	12.958	.011	Reject H_0 Significant
2	34	46.03				
3	25	34.12				
4	8	25.31				
5	4	58.38				

Note: p-value $\leq .05$ – Significant; p-value $> .05$ – Not Significant

Castro et al. (2024) conducted a phenomenological study revealing the significant challenges teachers face when teaching multiple subject areas. Thematic analysis identified key difficulties, including extensive preparation demands, varied teaching materials, and the need for diverse instructional methods. Teachers also reported that insufficient subject mastery rendered this practice ineffective. This issue has major implications for education in the Philippines, where it is common to assign teaching loads beyond teachers' areas of expertise.

The study by Velasco (2020) revealed that multi-grade and multiple-subject handling teachers face numerous challenges, including insufficient time for lesson preparation, low self-confidence in teaching out-of-field subjects, limited subject mastery, difficulties with

time management and work-life balance, stress and mental health issues, and inadequate access to healthcare.

Difference between Public High School Teachers’ Quality of Teaching when Grouped According to Profile Variables

The table summarizes the results of testing the differences between public high school teachers’ *quality of teaching* when grouped according to profile variables. Among the variables, only the *number of teaching loads* significantly influences quality of teaching. This highlights the significant role of workload balance in maintaining high teaching standards. Excessive teaching loads may reduce teachers’ capacity to deliver quality teaching, while lighter loads may allow for more preparation and focus.

Variable	Test	p	Interpretation
Gender	$U = 476.0$.194	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Age	$H = 5.601$.587	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Civil Status	$H = 4.725$.094	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Position	$H = .827$.661	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Number of Years in Service	$H = 6.736$.565	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Number of Preparations/Subjects Taught	$H = 7.441$.114	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	$H = 14.794$.039	Reject H_0 ; Significant
Number of Ancillary Services Assigned	$H = 6.215$.184	Do Not Reject H_0 ; Not Significant

Note: p-value $\leq .05$ – Significant; p-value $> .05$ – Not Significant

The table below shows that there is a significant difference between public school teachers’ quality of teaching when grouped according to number of teaching loads, $H(7, N = 77) = 14.794, p = .039$, thus, null hypothesis was rejected. This finding suggests that the number of teaching loads has a significant effect on the quality of teaching among teachers. Differences in teaching loads may correlate with variations in teaching quality, indicating that teachers with heavier or lighter loads may experience differing impacts on their effectiveness to teach.

Teaching Loads	N	Mean Rank	df	χ^2	p	Interpretation
1	1	67.00	7	14.794	.039	Reject H_0 ; Significant
2	8	37.06				
3	3	41.17				
4	17	32.71				
5	16	53.44				
6	28	33.20				
7	3	54.33				
8	1	12.50				

Note: p-value $\leq .05$ – Significant; p-value $> .05$ – Not Significant

Tarraya (2023) reviewed existing literature and studies that highlight the negative effects of heavy workloads and extended working hours on teachers. These pressures adversely impact teachers' mental and physical health, work performance, personal lives, and student achievement. Increased workloads, often mandated by policymakers, contribute to teacher burnout, which in turn lowers job satisfaction and teaching effectiveness. Additionally, the excessive allocation of tasks hinders teachers' ability to manage their time and emotions, ultimately reducing their overall classroom efficiency and effectiveness.

Relationship between Public High School Teachers’ Welfare and their Quality of Teaching

Correlational analysis results showed a moderate, positive correlation between the two variables, $r_s = .42, p < .001$, suggesting a statistically significant relationship. The positive correlation implies that higher levels of welfare are associated with higher quality teaching practices. This finding highlights the role of teacher welfare in supporting effective teaching outcomes.

Spearman’s rho		Interpretation
Coefficient correlation	.421**	Moderate correlation
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Reject H_0 ; Significant
N	77	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The study of Ashaba et al. (2020) found that secondary school teachers have moderate levels of welfare in areas like housing, allowances, medical care, school environment, meals, transport, training, classroom conditions, and government policies. Their job effectiveness was also rated as moderate, with a moderate positive link between welfare and performance. To enhance teacher effectiveness and satisfaction, timely payment of salaries and allowances is essential. Providing housing, meals, and other support is

also recommended to boost morale, motivation, and commitment to educational goals.

Rwigema's (2022) study on how teachers' welfare affects the quality of education also emphasizes that teachers' welfare—such as timely salary payments, promotions, benefits, and professional training—plays an essential role in enhancing academic achievement. School administrators and policymakers are encouraged to establish comprehensive welfare packages that address teachers' diverse needs and support school objectives. These packages should motivate teachers to remain committed, improve their skills, and promote positive change in schools. Professional development programs and performance rewards, whether financial or through improved working conditions, are essential for sustaining teacher motivation and creativity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, removing administrative tasks from teachers' responsibilities could have a substantial positive impact on both their welfare and the quality of their teaching. Teachers in this study are already balancing multiple responsibilities, including teaching and ancillary tasks such as class advisorship and coordinators. The removal of administrative duties would allow teachers to dedicate more time and energy to their core teaching functions. Additionally, teachers' overall welfare could improve if lawmakers review areas related to salary, health, and retirement benefits, which were identified as lower-rated aspects of teachers' welfare.

Moreover, removing the administrative burden would likely enhance the quality of teaching, as the study found a significant difference between the number of teaching loads and teaching quality. With no administrative tasks assigned, teachers would have more time to focus on content and pedagogy, leading to improved teaching practices, better learning environments, and greater opportunities for personal growth. Furthermore, the positive correlation between teachers' welfare and quality of teaching suggests that as teachers' welfare improves, so too does their teaching effectiveness.

To promote a more supportive work environment, school leaders should refrain from reassigning administrative tasks to teachers. By doing so, teachers will have more time to focus on their professional development, enhance their teaching skills, and ultimately improve student outcomes.

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